

TEACHING AND PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING IN THE CLASSROOM IS AN IMPORTANT LEADER IN THE FIELD OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *This article is one of the topical problems of our time. It focuses on such issues as the system of educational work carried out by the class teacher with students, a deeper and more serious approach of the class teacher to the planning of educational work, and the development of the life of the class team. The features of the systematic improvement of the activities of the class teacher in the pedagogical and psychological study of students and the interaction of the class teacher with students are highlighted in detail.*

Keywords: *education, upbringing, social, political, legal, psychological, pedagogical, economic, medical and environmental, family, neighborhood, school, teacher, student.*

Currently, in accordance with measures to increase the capacity of pedagogical personnel and in the period of rapid and globalization, where fundamental reforms are taking place, the systematic improvement of the activities of the head of the class, who can study the activities of students both psychologically and pedagogically, is one of the urgent tasks of today. The Ush envisions the owner of this task as a supervisor-educator, who is largely guided by the educational process. However, it is impossible to achieve a pedagogical goal by separating upbringing from education, education from upbringing. The study of the personality of the reader has always been the focus of our pedagogical and psychological scientists. Kamoliddin Husayn, a qomusian scholar, noted the special role of the school and teacher in the upbringing of children in the work of Preacher Ali-Koshifi, writing: "it is necessary for the coach to follow the rules of grace and decency in exhortation and education, it is not suitable to give him a pand in public places, but to speak to the child in a deserted place. It is necessary to approach him politely if there is an opportunity to give an admonition, because in our time it is advisable to be polite and empathetic"

The famous educator Abdullah Avlani also gives a special place in his works to express the views on the personality of the teacher and his activities. Alloma notes that the role of the teacher in the development of a child's mental state is incomparable if parents play a specific role in the growth of the child in health. In particular, the formation of the mental abilities of children is a "sacred task that rests on the attention of teachers, is assigned to their conscience", "depends on the strength, elegance, breadth of Thought, on the upbringing of the teacher."

From these points presented above, we can know that our qomusiy scientists also insist on the need to respectfully approach the personality of the child in education, upbringing of students.

A number of pedagogical scientists have been working in our republic to study the activities of the head of the class. S. Temurova, A.Khayitov, S.Muhammadiyeva Z.Lambiev, G.Mo' minova, N.Saidakhmedov, G.A.Sultanova, O'.Tolipov, M.Gurbanov, H.Ibragimov, M.S.Zakharina, H. Sonakulov, A.Mirkosimov, A.Musurmonova, A.K.Munavvarov, K.Mahmudovs and others carried out research work on the system of educational work in which the head of the Class conducts the educational process with students. Hususan K.Hoshimov and S.The nishanova

textbook" History of Pedagogy " provides information on how educational training of students was carried out at all times.

M.O'.Askarova and M.The khayitboevs 'textbook" pedagogy "reflected on the effectiveness of implementation in the study of students on the basis of the concept of" family, neighborhood, school cooperation", which distinguishes family, neighborhood, school education and tasks. Based on the opinion of scientists, the effectiveness of family, neighborhood, school cooperation when following the following tamoils is reflected in the case of high ol.

- The participants in the process of cooperation in the field of education and training are the actions of fig work unit;

- rights and duties of the parties in cooperation of the teacher and the student;

-in the process of education, the interests of the state and the nation are always united; the implementation of a social function, based on such principles, presupposes the creation of conditions for the worthy development of the child in the existing social economic conditions. The deeper and more serious the class leader approaches the planning of educational work, the easier the life of the class team will develop.

In upbringing, the child plays an important role of blowing on account of interest and inclinations.

In addition to increasing the educational and educational level of the student, the head of the class has a joint role in the task of protecting him from external influences, in which the task of social protection of the student from the negative impact of the environment is a priority. Social protection is a system of practical social, political, legal, psychological, pedagogical, economic, medical and environmental measures, violation of children's rights and human dignity in physical, mental and spiritual and moral formation, development, normal conditions, consciously regulated.

The role of class leaders in improving the quality of education should also be reflected in the work plan. The following principles were considered important in the activities of class leaders:

- setting goals, taking into account a certain situation, capabilities;

- adherence to the principle of continuity;

- consistency-the inclusion of all participants in the process of achieving the goal; accuracy-the direction of achieving a possible result;

- implementation and justification of goals based on the constant study of the needs and capabilities of all participants in the Diagnostic and pedagogical process;

From these views, it can be seen that students initially do not fully feel the responsibility they have, they may not know what ability the importance of obtaining science has of themselves. Therefore, our sons and daughters need adult support, care until they choose an independent life path. Considering that their main time is spent at school, in this regard, it becomes clear how wide the scope of the tasks for the head of the class is. The role of the class leader is great in creating the necessary conditions for students to manage the educational process, form a stable team in the classroom, fully demonstrate their abilities. Because it is the main intermediary that unites the educational goals of peoples, parents, science teachers, school psychologists, in general, each responsible person, who are involved in the fate of young people.

Young people have a strong passion for realizing being, mastering the secrets of science, becoming a mature person in the future. But since those who do not have enough experience in what way the goal should be achieved, it is necessary to start them on the right path. To do this, first of all, let the head of the class be a personal example for students. Because the child constantly

monitors the behavior of the teacher, is interested in his personal life. With a culture of dress and treatment, in the neighborhood, in the family, an educator who sets an example for students, distinguished by personal qualities, wins the trust and respect of students. From these considerations we give the class leader the following definitions:

The head of the class ensures the participation of students in the supervisory educational process (monitors attendance, promotes the creation of a ksracky environment for students, determines the attitude of students to parents, neglects the educational process, irresponsibility, disrespect for classmates and teachers, works alone with students who are manning it).

The head of the class forms interest and desire for study among students of the beginner-grade country of science (carries out educational activities, introducing parents to the requirements imposed on students. Help students work independently.).

Class leader moral, exemplary, spiritual teacher conducts individual, collective conversations with students about their rights and duties, evaluates their discipline, organizes various activities on moral, social, legal topics, etc.) in resolving conflicts between students and teachers, compliance with internal procedures in the educational process, violation or violation of moral norms and internal procedures.

The head of the class the cultural person organizes an educational process with Universal and cultural values, conducts excursions with students, conducts conversations on the topic of culture, organizes cultural events at the school.

The head of the class social educator talks with students about changes in the course of life in society, helping them to enter into social relationships.

A close friend of the students, the head of the class, helps students to engage in various activities, takes part of the care for students (in the group, ja moavi inspires the organization of creative activities, helps students to self-understand, self-evaluate, focus their opportunity and attention on some activity (work alone with a student). The main tasks of class leaders operating in secondary schools today are as follows:

- Organization of the practically established education and upbringing of students of the class attached to him as one of the base educators in the educational system of the educational institution (next referred to as students of the class);

- strictly follow the culture of treatment and dress according to the rules of etiquette and internal order, to be exemplary in the team;

- to awaken in their hearts such qualities as national pride, patriotism, kindness, responsibility, initiative, business acumen, on the basis of an individual approach to students in need of help;

- working in cooperation with teachers, youth leaders, psychologists, parents and their dying persons (next referred to as parents), juvenile affairs commissions through the leadership of the educational institution, neighborhood, law enforcement drugs, relevant state and non-governmental organizations in the organization of spiritual and educational education of students;

- cooperation in the work carried out between minors on the implementation of legislation on the Prevention of uncontrolled and violations of minors, on the Prevention of crime and offenses among students.

Class leaders can also perform other tasks in accordance with the legislation.

Class leaders carry out the following functions in accordance with the main tasks assigned to them:

- to carry out the upbringing of a fully mature, harmonious-spiritual, mental, physically developed personality in every possible way, to create the appropriate conditions for the full manifestation of the abilities of students of the class;

- to establish an approach to the organization of educational work in the collective cooperation of educators and students, depending on the specifics of each student;

- ensure the full participation of students of the class in the morning deployments in the prescribed manner;

- ensure the maintenance and efficient use of existing equipment in the attached classroom;

- class leaders organize their activities on the basis of comprehensive educational work and specific criteria, taking into account the age characteristics, general level of development and abilities of students.

The head of the class increases the educational and educational level of the student, in addition, it has a co-role in the task of protecting him from external influences, in which the task of social protection of the student from the negative impact of the environment is a priority. Social protection is a system of practical social, political, legal, psychological, pedagogical, economic, medical and environmental measures, violation of children's rights and human dignity in physical, mental and spiritual and moral formation, development, normal conditions, consciously regulated. The implementation of a social function implies the creation of conditions for the worthy development of the child in the existing social economic conditions.

The diagnostic function, on the other hand, implies the identification of the initial stage in the state of students (mental, mental, moral) by the head of the class and the constant identification of changes in the education of students. It is aimed at studying the personality and individuality of the child, analyzing them, looking for the reasons for the inefficiency of the results obtained and describing the holistic pedagogical process. The diagnostic task of class leaders is carried out in the following areas:

- collect information on the student, his family and parents, the class community; aimed at looking for reasons for inefficiency and describing the holistic pedagogical process. The diagnostic task of class leaders is carried out in the following areas:

- collect information on the student, his family and parents, the class community;
- preliminary diagnostic data with the next one; to conduct an analysis on the degree of appropriation, determination of negative and negative aspects of individual development;

- understanding the content by understanding the changes that are taking place; diagnostic process, parents and other teachers of students on the subjects of the subject;

- examination of the subject's objectivity through various diagnostic methods, etc. In the comprehensive study of students of the class, the content of the activities of the class leader is made up of:

1. Class executive's work with the student community

2. The work of the class leader with parents

3. Activities in extracurricular and extracurricular activities

The use of interactive methods in solving these problems "is the fifth (sixth, seventh,...) over-targeting. This method is of particular importance when students acquire the skills of logical thinking. When applying it, performing the following actions will give good results. It serves to reveal the content of the topic to readers when explaining the topic.

- Entrust readers with the task of identifying a concept that does not apply to the topic and excluding it from the system;

- It is necessary to encourage students to interpret the essence of their actions (in order to strengthen the topic, students should also comment on the concepts preserved in the system and demand that they justify the logical link between them).

Between concepts that illuminate the essence of the topic logical links that the middle of the musical dasataval get justification forms in students the skills of independent thinking, substantiating their personal approaches, as well as comparing their personal reflections with those of their peers. The main function of the class leader is to organize, direct and coordinate all educational work in the class attached to him. The head of the class begins in his activities by studying his class and, separately, any student. The head of the class will help to effectively use visual weapons, use students' free time from class and grow children's creative abilities, comprehensively maturing them. He enters into an individual and collective relationship with students when performing this function. The content of the duty of the head of the class in the process of educational work is associated with the organization of spiritual educational work. According to him, students of a comprehensive school must grow up competent for "living strong, educated, wise and of course happy." To do this, it is necessary to establish educational work based on the principles of vigilance, sensitivity, decisiveness and responsiveness of the class leader.

When, in the process of educational work, the leader of the class fulfills his duty, the expected result can be achieved. In this sense, elementary students are teachers and mentors for their class, and senior leaders are mentors and teachers for students. When the head of the class does not fulfill his duty in educational work, the spiritual atmosphere in the classroom is disturbed, educational efficiency is impaired, and the moral development of students is cracked. In the pedagogical and psychological study of students, the existing prerequisite conditions for improving the activities of the class leader were studied in detail.

In the study of students in secondary schools, a systematic development of the activities of class leaders was determined if parents, the pedagogical team of the school, work together and establish their own cooperation.

Various methodological recommendations for organizing educational classes, the use of interactive methods, the use of sample lesson developments of educational lessons and events gave effective results when working with the class team.

By forming the concepts of spiritual moral education in the conduct of educational classes in primary school students, the content of the qualities of patriotism, hard work, humanity, harmony in them further improves the work of the class leader.

It would be advisable to conclude on this problem as follows. In the case of appointment to the role of class leader, it is important that their individual characteristics: the management of the team, the responsiveness of the state of spiritual upbringing is considered as the main criterion. It is advisable to master the activities of class leaders with a highly qualified, positive result and experience, as well as the effective methods of foreign experience. In accordance with the purpose of popularizing the activities of the class leaders in the district, city, region and Republic, the implementation of such activities will be a solid foundation for the formation of feelings of love for the motherland of young people.

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